

Deployment of Enterprise Architecture for Management of Digital Services in Smart Cities

Bokolo Anthony Jrn. *, Sobah Abbas Petersen, Eldar Hauge Torkelsen

Department of Computer Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

Abstract

Over the years Enterprise Architecture (EA) has become an intensively researched and applied approach aimed at managing transformation of cities into smart cities. Thus, most cities are deploying EA as an approach to manage enterprise's implementation of Information Technology (IT). While many cities deploy EA, there are initiatives that impacts the value that can be derived when EA is deployed for management of digital services in smart cities. Therefore, this article explores the current practice of EA by practitioners and stakeholders involved in smart city project through qualitative data via survey research method. Findings from this study discuss the importance of EA and provides practical insights on EA deployment in smart cities. Thus, enabling municipalities to focus and better plan on how to anticipate and prepare for digital change during smart city development. Besides, the findings provide IT managers, enterprise architect, and urban planners with evidence of how EA can facilitate implementation of digital services in smart cities.

Keywords: Information systems; Enterprise architecture deployment; Practitioners; Digital services; Smart cities; qualitative data

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +47-41398239; fax: +47-41398239.
E-mail address: anthony.j.bokolo@ntnu.no

1. Introduction

Over the decade there is increased research on Enterprise Architecture (EA) deployment among academia and industry [1]. EA aims to achieve goal-oriented coherent and organizational structures, processes, information provision, and technology management. EA describes the essential structure of an organization and supports institutional transformation by providing a holistic view on as-is as well as to-be processes and structures. EA is the representation of the behavior and structure of an enterprise's business environment in relation to its IT landscape. It depicts the current and future deployment of IT in the enterprise and specifies a roadmap to attain future state [2]. EA also enhances strategies and provides informed business, operations, and IT decision that enhances institutions to accomplish their objectives [3]. EA underpins managerial decisions relating to applications, data, human infrastructure and technical infrastructure, and management responsibilities [4].

Also, existing literature on EA deployment are concerned into how enterprises sustain their EA strategies [2]. In urban context an effective EA is vital to smart city's survival and success [1]. The deployment of EA has some significant strategic value for cities, such as strategic agility and better operational management. But irrespective of the benefits to be attained, EA is not widely adopted when cities want to implement digital services to citizens. This may be due to difficulties or issues faced in deploying EA in smart cities [5]. Nonetheless, while extant studies have researched on the potential, costs, and benefits of EA, the practice of EA particularly in smart cities has not been empirically explored [6]. Furthermore, it remains challenging for practitioners to effectively deploy EA in their urban process [7]. Thus, there is still a call for research on how EA is deployed in the public sector specifically in urban context [3]. This article aims at providing knowledge on the practice of EA deployment from smart city perspective. To be more specific, this study seeking an answer to the research question:

- What is the current practice of enterprise architecture in smart city domain?

Hence this current study carries out a research grounded on qualitative data via survey research method to provide practical empirical evidence on issues faced when EA is employed by practitioners involved in making cities smarter. This article is arranged as follows: In the next section, the theoretical background is described. In section 3 the research methodology adopted is discussed. Section 4 is the results. Section 5 is the discussion and implications of study. Finally, the conclusion, limitations, and future works are presented in section 6.

2. Theoretical Background

This section presents an overview of smart cities, the role of EA in smart cities, and related works that employed EA in public and private sectors similar to this current study.

2.1. Overview of Smart Cities

A smart city is a city that employs smartness in its governance, living, economy, mobility, people, and environment towards improvement of its citizens and stakeholders [8]. Smart city deploys Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in several areas within the city such as in transportation, health, services, and facilities to improve the economic, social, environmental, and technological aspect of the city [9]. Accordingly, deployment of ICT is becoming a tool for the digital transformation of cities into smart cities. Thus, ICT directly and indirectly leads to smart city development by improving the lives of residents, enhancing innovation growth, increasing resource efficiency, and generating new jobs [8]. Researchers such as Sobczak [8] argued that smart cities should not be conceptualized only based on their physical structure but should be seen like a huge network of digitally and seamlessly connected systems of systems. Smart cities enable the optimization of urban's resource use and the decrease of negative rebound effects that impacts proper functioning of the city in connection to the goals of sustainable development [10]. Smart cities aimed to safeguard and preserve the natural environment while utilizing its resources to address present needs of the society [8]; [9].

2.2. Role of Enterprise Architecture in Smart Cities

EA provides a formal description of the present and possible future state(s) of a city, and a managed transformation roadmap between these states to meet citizens and other stakeholders' goals thus creating value to the city [5]. EA comprises of models, principals, and methods that are employed in the design and actualization of an institution's structure, technologies, business processes, and information systems [11]. EA deployment facilitates a flexible and stable environment, leading to digital innovation and transformation consequently supporting enterprise flexibility and stability [4].

Additionally, EA deployment enables enterprises to decrease IT business alignment risks, improved flexibility for enterprises that provide digital services by accelerating digital innovation, bridging gaps between business and IT, and enabling appropriate business and environmental changes [12]. In urban context, EA is mostly adopted as a method to manage digital transformations of cities [1]; [13], towards fostering business and IT alignment. EA provides communication and documentation of the current enterprise processes/structures, support for the deployment of to-be processes/structures, and support for city transformation into future structures/processes [14].

2.3. Related Work on Enterprise Architecture in Public and Private Sectors

Over the decades, several studies have employed EA to achieve competitive advantage in organizations. Among these studies Al-Kharusi et al. [11] examined stakeholders and enterprise architects towards an alignment framework for EA development. The authors designed an alignment framework to support EA development procedure with the stakeholders to achieve an architecture to provide guidance grounded on qualitative case study and data collected from 15 interviews conducted with the stakeholders and architects. Kotusev and Kurnia [15] conducted a comprehensive review and taxonomy of theoretical foundation of EA. The researchers provided a critical understanding of EA practice. Their study provided theoretical insights on EA research and contributed to the development of a theoretical basis for EA discipline.

Mirsalari and Ranjbarfard [2] developed a model for evaluation of EA quality. The purpose of the study aimed to specify EA quality attributes and its evaluation metrics within organizations. The model helps organizations to assess the quality of the deployed EA or as-is status of EA and provides the phase required to improve the current practice. Anthony Jnr et al. [16] employed Application Programming Interface (API) to examine big data management to achieve sustainable energy prosumption services in smart cities based on a developed EA framework.

Weiss and Winter [17] developed a measurement items for the institutionalization of EA management in enterprises. The research contributed to assess and inform EA management design from several, moderately new perspectives. Aier et al. [14] presented a classification of EA scenarios based on an exploratory analysis. The study presented three different EA scenarios and further provided the foundation for situational EA approach engineering.

Van Der Raadt et al. [18] investigated stakeholder perception towards EA. The authors aimed at achieving organizational goal and collaboration between EA stakeholders and architects. Arbab et al. [19] explored the integrating architectural models symbolic, subjective models, and semantic in EA. The study made a difference between 3 classes of models. Findings from the reviewed seven studies suggest that the main contributions in EA are mostly grounded on secondary data and studies that empirically report on current EA initiatives being deployed in organizational context, but studies on urban context are limited [20]. Therefore, there is need for research that offers qualitative evidence linking EA application to smart city development.

3. Methods

This study employs qualitative and interpretive research method using semi-structured interview to collect data similar to prior study [21] via survey employed as the research method based on purposive sampling of respondents from 18 organizations in Norway and Ireland involved in the smart city project +CityxChange (<https://cityxchange.eu/>) where an EA framework was developed as presented in [22].

Qualitative method is adopted in this study as it provides an in-depth understanding about the phenomena that is being explored such as the deployment of EA for management of digital services in smart cities. The data collection took place between November 2020 to January 2021 by the means of the online survey questionnaire. Invitations were sent in November 2020 and in January 2021 additionally reminder was sent to participants to partake in the survey. The request to partake and provide data was sent to 40 prospective participants involved in the in the smart city project +CityxChange. The first part of the data collection instrument prompt a question to (*Consent for participation in the study: I have received and understood information about the project to provide feedback on Enterprise Architecture Framework*), request for the consent of the respondents to participate in providing data stating that their participation is voluntary. After sending the request 2 consecutive times only 13 participants responded to the invitation to provide data as regards to quantitative and qualitative questions. But only the qualitative questions are reported in this study as shown in Table 1. The data helps towards the validation of the EA framework that was developed in the +CityxChange project [22], which comprises of seven layers (context, service, business, application and data processing, data space, technologies, and physical infrastructures), and perspectives (stakeholder and data).

The collected qualitative data was analyzed using descriptive and narrative analysis and the data provided by the participants were clustered based on their reply to the questions presented in Table 1. Data saturation was achieved as similar data was collected from the respondents who are all consortium partners within the +CityxChange smart city project.

Table 1. Interview questions.

Questions
What information would you like to capture using an EA framework when developing digital services in smart cities?
What techniques does your organisation use to document knowledge that individuals have learnt during a project? e.g interviews, observations or writing documentation.
What techniques does your organisation use to share knowledge? e.g., collaboration, training, or meetings.
Apart from the EA framework, does your organisation use any other architecture for other means? If so, how does it relate to EA framework and can they be combined?
Which problems do you think enterprise architecture can or should attempt to solve?
If you have any other feedback or comments, please add them here.

4. Results

The qualitative data collected from survey provides new insights on the application of EA in smart cities. All responses from the qualitative data were collected as feedback provided from 13 participants. Table 2 provides an overview of participants information.

4.1. Findings from Demographic Data

Table 2 depicts the demographic information of the 13 participants who provided data on their current EA practice in a smart city project. Findings from Table 2 suggest that majority of the participants are male as compared to female. Regarding the age, 5 participants were among 41 - 50 years, 4 participants are aged from 20 - 30 years, 3 participants are among the age of 31 - 40 years, only 1 participant is aged between 51 - 60 years. The results show that 5 participants have 6 months to 1-year experience with EA, whereas 4 participants have less than 6 months experience. Also, 3 participants have 1 to 3 years' experience and only 1 participant have 4 to 5 years' experience with adopting EA.

The results show that 10 participants have 1 to 3 years' experience with smart city projects, whereas 2 participants have 4 - 5 years' experience and only 1 participant have less than 1 year experience with smart city projects. Regarding the primary role of the respondents' organisations, the respondents are researchers, technical architect, full-stack developer, managing director, software developer, and project engineer. Considering the type of organization, 7 respondents currently work in private organizations, whereas 3 respondents currently work in the universities, and 2 work in research organizations. Lastly, only 1 of the respondents works in city council or municipality.

Results from Table 2 as regards to type of services the respondent's organisation primarily provide suggest that 4 of the respondents are into research focusing on citizen engagement, economics, planning, data analytics, public services such as in smart housing, smart transport or roads, environmental protection, efficient water use etc. and smart city related services. Besides, 3 of the respondents provide innovative services and another 3 respondents provide data related services. Additionally, 2 respondents provide ICT infrastructure related services, and 1 respondent provides energy related service to citizens in smart cities.

Table 2. Demographic information of the participants.

Gender	Age	Type of organisation	Type of services your organisation primarily provide	Primary role in your organisation	Experience in using enterprise architecture	Experience related to smart city projects
Male	31 - 40 years	Research	Provide data	Researcher	1 - 3 years	1 - 3 years

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Male	41 - 50 years	organisation University	related services Innovation related services	Senior Researcher	1 - 3 years	1 - 3 years
Male	41 - 50 years	Research organisation	ICT Infrastructure related services	Technical Architect	6 months to 1 year	4 - 5 years
Male	31 - 40 years	Private organisation	ICT Infrastructure related services	Full stack developer	6 months to 1 year	1 - 3 years
Female	41 - 50 years	University	Research focusing on citizen engagement	Researcher	6 months to 1 year	1 - 3 years
Male	20 - 30 years	University	Innovation related services	Developing Sustainable Energy Services	Less than 6 months	1 - 3 years
Male	51 - 60 years	Private organisation	Economics, planning, and data analytics	Managing Director	Less than 6 months	1 - 3 years
Male	41 - 50 years	City council or municipality	Public services (housing, roads, environmental, water etc.)	Developing Digital Services	1 - 3 years	1 - 3 years
Male	20 - 30 years	Private organisation	Data related	Conducting research, data analysis and interpretation	6 months to 1 year	1 - 3 years
Male	41 - 50 years	Private organisation	Innovation related	Innovator	Less than 6 months	4 - 5 years
Male	31 - 40 years	Private organisation	Data related	IT Manager	4 - 5 years	1 - 3 years
Male	20 - 30 years	Private organisation	Energy related	Software Developer	Less than 6 months	1 - 3 years
Male	20 - 30 years	Private organisation	Smart city services	Project Engineer	6 months to 1 year	Less than 1 year

4.2. Descriptive Analysis of Qualitative Data

For the first question the additional information that the respondents would like to capture using EA framework in developing digital services in smart cities. *"The researcher stated that the EA framework model can be useful but there is still some learning curve to understand in properly deploying it and even a steeper one to be able to use it". Also, "the researcher mentioned that EA framework is not suitable for non-practitioners". Likewise, "the full-stack developer stated that the EA framework should be presented in a form that is easily understood by those not familiar with EA" as a concept to improve its adoption in providing digital services in smart cities.*

For the second question what techniques the respondent's organisation uses to document knowledge that individuals have learnt during EA adoption. Findings from the respondents stated that they utilize user manuals, observations, internal document/written documentation in a web-based corporate wiki, interviews, structured surveys, workshops, using the Delphi method. They also use discussions and project team meeting when each project is closed, where details of lessons learned are discussed and captured.

Considering the techniques, the respondents organisation uses to share knowledge on EA adoption for smart city development. Findings suggest that internal document templates, Wiki, meetings, and informal discussions, co-design workshops using digital whiteboards, collaboration, and training.

Findings from the respondents mentioned that apart from the EA framework, their organisation use other architecture for other means. Where the researcher mentioned that *"Yes his organization uses a frameworks and tools relevant to the established enterprise architectures such as TOGAF which is an EA framework that provides model and tool that can be specifically used with other EA frameworks".* Although, the managing director *"stated that at the moment they do not really use other EA frameworks, but his organization intend to use the developed EA frameworks proposed in the +CityxChange smart city project going forward to better align their ICT processes and business systems, starting with staff data".*

Based on the fifth questions exploring problems the respondents think EA can or should attempt to solve. One of the researchers mentioned that *"EA should introduce frameworks and tools for determining and implementing application and technology architecture, data governance, data interoperability, data security and risk management, relevant regulatory compliance, knowledge retention and in general digital transformation".* Also, the other researcher stated that *"EA should be able to support the defining of blueprint service architecture".* The Technical Architect and Full-stack developer highlighter that *"EA should facilitate high level planning and design" and also "depict how different organisations can work together towards the same goal".* Furthermore, the managing director pointed out that *"EA should be able to address duplication of ICT systems and data" and the project engineer stated that "EA should improve the overall understanding of architecture and forwarding and sharing of knowledge within smart city projects".*

Based on the last question one of the researchers stated that *“the terms used within the data collection instrument are difficult for beginners, non-technical synonyms could be used to simplify the data collection of evidence as related to EA practice adoption for provision of digital services in smart cities”*.

5. Discussion and Implications of Study

As cities continue to experience digital transformation by providing digital services to their citizens in becoming smart cities [13], EA is deployed to facilitate the digitalization of urban services. This study investigates EA deployment focusing on the role of EA to support the management of digital services in smart cities. EA deployment can help IT managers and urban planners to provide understanding on how to address complexity issues from an ambiguous and abstract state to a more clear and less technical format. Therefore, this study explores the current practice of EA by IT practitioners and stakeholders involved in smart city project through qualitative data via survey research method.

Findings from this study provides recommendations on how enterprises in cities that provide digital services can assess their readiness in deploying enterprise architecture. Therefore, enterprises will be able to assess their readiness in advance before deploying EA in practice, and better understand the gaps that needs to be addressed. Findings from the literature [23] argued that EA enhances enterprise’s IT capabilities and is seen as an indispensable practice aimed at improving enterprise agility. Again, it is observed that findings from this study are congruent with earlier studies [24]; [25] which mentioned that EA defines the present and desirable future states of an enterprise’s capabilities, processes, systems, application, data, and IT infrastructure providing a roadmap for attaining this target from the present state.

Findings from this study also confirms that EA attempts to address enterprise issues as pointed out by Anthony Jnr. [1], where the author stated that EA describes the enterprise level, associated data employed within smart city and the relationships among the employed data used to provide digital services. Overall, this study contributes to practice by providing a broader view of role of EA in supporting knowledge management and transfer to improve digital services in smart cities, thus highlighting the capabilities of EA in urban context. From a theoretical point of view, the findings are relevant to researcher as it provides issues that need to be addressed in EA adoption within smart cities that can be further explored by academicians.

6. Conclusion

Enterprise architecture is a practice intended to enhance the management of complex information systems and business strategies [26]. Although EA is widely deployed in different institutions, researchers and practitioners have acknowledge that there is a current lack of empirically validated

research on EA grounded on qualitative data which provides evidence on how EA contributes to improve digital services in smart cities. Therefore, this study adds to the existing body of knowledge by exploring the current practice of EA by IT practitioners and stakeholders involved in smart city project through qualitative data via semi-structured interview. Evidence from this research present initiatives that impacts the value that can be derived when EA is deployed for management of digital services in smart cities.

The study provides current practice of EA to make cities smarter as a lesson that can be useful to both technical and non-technical practitioners involved in provision of digital services in smart cities. The findings intended to foster and provide more understanding on how enterprises that provide digital services in smart cities and also improve their services. Additionally, this research is based on evidence from Norway and Ireland. Thus, the interpretation of the findings should be confined to these two countries or to areas with similar smart city adoption practice. Further, this research provides qualitative findings only, its credibility needs to be improved by further quantitative empirical evidence. Thus, future work will carry out a cross-sectional survey using questionnaire instrument to further validate EA deployment practice in smart cities for management of digital services.

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